

Studies in Educational Management

2019 (3) 26–37

EUROKD

Improving communication between parents and siblings

Leticia Escardó^{*1}, Christine Lester

General Secretary of Fundacion Belen
Chief Executive Minister Development Centre

Received 23 August 2019 *Accepted* 11 October 2019

ABSTRACT

DIR aims to increase the communication skills of stressed parents and teenagers by the teaching of senior volunteers transformed in coaches through the experience of an intangible European cultural heritage: the art of cooking and dinner together.

Our first questionnaire revealed, as we expected, a reluctance to discuss major issues of relevance, a mis-match in what the issues actually were, even the involvement of grandparents or the extended family. In some parents an abdication of parental concern, citing the parents lack of confidence in their own ability, a willingness to leave it to experts and teachers. Our results so far (we have another 12 months to continue our project) lead us to believe that a communicational learning pathway is needed carried out by mentors and senior volunteers. We anticipate the results of our project to be a better understanding of the development needs of parents of disenfranchised adolescents.

Keywords: Communication, Family, Questionnaires, Learning by doing

Starting a European project is an adventure

It all began while analyzing hundreds of queries received by Fundacion Belen during the last five years. Fundacion Belen, is a Spanish private foundation which has been providing free advice and counselling to mothers with problematic children for over 23 years. 56% of these queries had a common problem around lack of personal communication tools within the family. This increasing personal non-communication brings solitude, misunderstanding and stress. It is apparent in many different countries across the world.

Correspond author E-mail address: info@fundacionbelen.org

As the lack of personal communication skill is such a common problem within the family the implementation solution needed to be tackled from different transnational points of view.

The project aims to increase the communication skills of stressed parents and teenagers by the teaching of senior volunteers transformed in coaches through the experience of an intangible European cultural heritage: the art of cooking and dinner together.

In a study done by Arroyo, Nevarez, Segrin, and Harwood (2012), results show that parent and teenagers lacking communication were negatively associated with their own social skills. Our first questionnaire revealed, as we expected, a reluctance to discuss major issues of relevance, a mismatch in what the issues were, even the involvement of grandparents or the extended family. In some parents an abdication of parental concern, citing the parents lack of confidence in their own ability and a willingness to leave it to experts and teachers. There are some classical studies as well that have been done on relationship between self-esteem and family communications. For example, Cooper, Holman, and Braithwaite (1983) concluded that those children who have little support from their parents reported a lower degree of self-esteem. According to the research of Demo, Small, and Savin-Williams (1987) self-perceptions of family relations, especially self-judgments of communication, are important in predicting levels of self-esteem for both adolescents and their parents. Also, Andrews and Duncan (1997) found that there is a relationship between self-esteem and family relations with drug abuse in adolescents.

Fundacion Belen identified that the possible solution could be implemented using “Dinner Is Ready” as a European Erasmus+ project. We reassembled our previous European partners to deliver this project and share the resultant solutions.

DIR project would intend to offer a new form of overcoming family uncommunication through an innovative educational approach “learning by doing” cooking and dinning together experience.

DIR has at the heart the objective to develop the most relevant personal skills, i.e. communication skills, in mothers of problematic children in order to foster their personal development, as well as to improve their participation in family, civic and social life; and will develop this skill through the experience of cultural competence: the art of cooking preparation together and having dinner together – thus improving the communication process.

DIR is a project under Erasmus+ Strategic Partnerships - supporting exchange of good practices and has the primary goal of developing and reinforcing the previously created network under a previous European Project (ESMV – Exercises to Stimulate & Motivate Volunteering - to develop new learning strategies. DIR will increase the partnership capacity to operate at transnational level, share and confront ideas, practices and methods.

A questionnaire was used to identify the greatest need and the best way for academic training for low- skilled families with teenagers who are uncommunicative

We would seek senior volunteers to be personal coaches for those mothers who have uncommunicative teenagers with or without behavioral problems and teaching them communication skills through the cooking together experiences. These experiences should be amusing, moments of hearty collaboration, of laughing together while cooking.

During the life of the project we have committed to: increase motivation on senior volunteers by teaching them how to become coaches. Adopt an inclusive approach (360-degree support mechanism of the family dynamic relationships) to bring about a fuller intervention targeted at the mothers, siblings & other family members by the agencies involved in bringing about a “prevention rather than punishment” culture. Enquiry for analyzing the best learning required at each country and family needs.

Improve future employability of the mothers or guardians to prepare them for beyond their caring role, developing their “University of Life experiences”. Plus develop peer-to-peer support groups for family members. Carry out an individual analysis to determine which type of learning would best suit each country and the family need. Develop on-line support mechanisms for the house-bound via volunteer infrastructure. Improve the quality of life relationships of problematic children/teenagers offering coaching and mentoring skills via senior volunteers.

The project will provide vocational and world of work training for both groups: senior volunteers and low skilled mothers while enhancing relationships between generations using the cooking experience as a wide-ranging topic. The learning by doing practice and training workshops to improve personal communication have been carry out between the strategic partners locally, nationally and European-wide.

DIR has been engaged since the first day of life in cultural diversity: exchange of good practices between partners to strengthen the strategic partnerships.

The partners

The institutions involved in the project have a proven understanding, good-will and hard work through the previous European Grundtvig project.

All of them work with volunteers as adult trainers. Through that previous Grundtvig project the partnership has achieved an increase in the level of their volunteers’ motivation.

The partners accepted and all the partnership during the first term started to look for investigations already done who could offer scientific evidence for our project.

The individual persons engaged in this project are:

Mr Jesus Saenz is a PHD Mining Engineer, Fundacion Belen President for the last 23 years; in charge of monitoring volunteers’ action and administrative matters, keeping in touch constantly with universities, Educational Authorities, and Social Welfare Institutions.

Mrs Leticia Escardo, myself, founder and General Secretary of Fundacion Belen, in charge of International and National Projects. Journalist, and Master in Computer Science by the Salamanca Pontifical University. She has been director for 15 years of *Cuenta y Razón* (a National Magazine of political and sociological essays). She has written in different national newspapers and is author of the book “*Como salir de una crisis*” (How to cope with a crisis), published by the Educational Authorities of Madrid ISBN 84-451-2682-2. “*Un siglo de España*” (A century in Spain). Ed Alianza 2002, ISBN 84-206-4144-8. “*La huella de Julian Marías: un pensador para la libertad*” (The trace of Julian Marias a freedom thinker”. Ed Comunidad de Madrid 2006. Legal Dep M-7419-2006. Mrs Escardo will be the contact person, the writer of communicational and educational materials

and the responsible for the dissemination planning as well as the DVDs and material to be hanged in the FB web site.

Mrs Christine Lester, coauthor in these paper, Chief Executive of a not-for-profit organisation committed to good governance, social inclusion, vision and values who, following 5 years development work with The Centre for Tomorrows Company in London on the inclusive approach (which includes Leadership at its center, stakeholder dialogue, employee engagement, customer service, suppliers network engagement and community. West Midlands Tomorrow has based most of its work around Leadership and Community issues. She is also Chief Executive of a limited company formed 30 years ago as a Vocational Guidance Centre. These are the skills she brings to the Dinner is Ready project. Prior to forming Minster she was a vocational teacher in Management, Leadership, Administration, Customer Service etc. and was heavily involved in the development of competence based education leading to the present National Vocational Qualifications and has done extensive work in projects being assimilated into the European Qualifications Framework. She is qualified in teaching in Further Education, Management and Business Studies, a qualified vocational assessor & internal verifier, and Adviser to Investors in People Award.

Our Organization Partners and their background, skills and what they bring to the project:

Minster Development Centre Ltd: Within first 12 months of its formation 30 years ago Minster was awarded a National Certificate of Recognition of Achievement for delivering a vocational award in an innovative manner – concentrating on organization objectives aligned with people development. Its founder qualified as an Investor in People Adviser and Assessor to organizations wishing to achieve a national standard. The greatest challenge was a 5-year strategic program for an old-style Cathedral and the 4th largest Diocese in the UK (Church of England) implementing change by recognizing the organization and 450 volunteers. This was achieved in 2002 & continues to be recognized. Minster has always concentrated on organizations slightly out of the normal with specific issues and the approach is to bring about culture change from top down, bottom up, engaging all levels in the vision of the future through people development. It has since carried out a Leonardo Partnership “Qualifying on the Spot” based on accreditation of prior learning (completed in 2010). Its sister organization West Midlands Tomorrow concentrates on vision and values & has also carried out Grundtvig Partnerships which has led to 5 other proposals. Minster has specific knowledge relating to the employment of volunteers in a social or caring capacity and links this background with its ability to strategically plan the learning process, developing people who can "train", writing the lesson plans & associated teaching aids, linking to available vocational education as career guidance & using a Lifetime Learning approach. It has also carried out extensive programs with ethnic communities in empowering, social inclusion and community leadership to better understand cultural differences in a caring environment. Minster will compare & contrast the competences existing for literacy, numeracy, IT & Communication, report on their suitability for family dynamics in the “home country language” & recommend new versions, if necessary, for accreditation. It will also advise & recommend on coaching & mentoring programs, volunteering accreditation for volunteers, ambassadors, stakeholders and a learning

pathway for the future employability of the family heads using the newly acquired life skills and recognition of the learning pathway for the beneficiaries of the program.

Previous projects - Tourist Guides for Intellectually Disabled in Europe – a 2-year project (Development of Innovation) where its role was based on its experience in developing a training needs analysis for special target sectors. Including tourism, culture & heritage; Therefore, MINSTER was the leader of WP - Development of the T-GUIDE Manual, Courseware, itinerary; the build-up of the “Skills/competences description” of the Tourist Guide for Intellectually Disabled it compiled and edited the T-GUIDE Manual (available in digital format, too) and the course content; developed the analysis of needs & accreditation where it existed. It related the T-Tourist Guide Manual to the European Quality Framework and led the work package of analysis of best practices across Europe and training needs analysis. It is presently delivering a Development of Innovation – strategic partnerships – around the rural economy – hospitality and catering with 8 other partner countries, developing new skills for young and experienced chefs

Minster was also involved in an interesting project to upskill people quickly and competently according to the EQF standards – QUOTS – “Qualifying on the Spot”, which lends itself to Dinner is Ready in that it uses the Accreditation of Prior Learning to identify and accredit skills which the parents may not be aware that they possess: We propose to review how this process through a Learning Pathway can motivate, give confidence and encourage the parents, volunteers (target group) to become not only a support to their children but also valuable members of an inclusive society in addition to creating career progression for the parents in later life.

ARVAR (The Association for Associative Life Renewal in Romania). The members of ARVAR have different professional backgrounds, being teachers, engineers, psychologists, artists or doctors, but they all share the common goals of reviving the community spirit and creating opportunities for the members of their communities to get involved in the improvement of community life, education and social inclusion for everybody, but especially for disadvantaged children and adults in Romania (people with various disabilities, children with social difficulties, orphans or from broken families).

Thanks to Foi et Migration Association most of the members of ARVAR attended trainings in France in the domain of education, medical sciences, pharmaceuticals, religion, group and project management. In France ARVAR members also participated in different activities organized by French NGOs such as Association des Grands Parents, Association Voir Anseble, Association Valentin Haüy, Association Auxilliers des Aveugles to the purpose of documenting and developing volunteering abilities of people of various backgrounds and ages. The core activities of ARVAR were developed based on the needs of visually-impaired children, their integration in the community, advice and support given to their families. To this purpose the Association developed a number of local and national activities and projects such as: Help them see the world (visits to museums, trips to various places of interest), Let us know our country (exchange visits for children from remote villages to Bucharest to visit it together with the visually-impaired/blind children, the latter being then taken to visit the villages); projects and camps for the visually-impaired developed together with the Scout Association; Parent Help (advice given to parents of

the visually-impaired – from the initial stages when they face the physical problems raised by their child's disability to the teenage period when they are confronted with the rebellion specific to this age and the lack of communication which can lead to depression on both sides, isolation and difficulty in finding one's right place in the world); continuous learning activities for members of the association, volunteers, educators and parents. ARVAR was a partner in the Grundtvig project named ESMV (Exercises to Stimulate Motivation on Volunteers) and co-ordinated by Fundacion Belen. This project was selected by the European Association of Educators for Adults (EAEA) among the ten best European projects. Some members of ARVAR have also acquired experience from other European funded projects at their place of work, mainly in The School for the Visually-impaired in Bucharest. These Erasmus+ projects (Robobraille or Inclutech) are meant to create facilities working on the computer for all sorts of disabled people or to create digital manuals for these people.

NALMA – NATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF FOLK HIGH SCHOOLS joins Lithuanian folk high schools. There are about 1,000 learners per year. The focus of folk high schools is to discover and strengthen the unique skills of each person in a challenging yet supportive social atmosphere. NALMA provides help and assistance to different socially disadvantaged groups, adults and youth, learns about other people and their lives –about yourself and your wishes in life, stimulates the development processes of free personality. Also, NALMA has the intention of organizing short-term courses such as new teaching methods, folk arts, foreign languages and cooking. NALMA aims to raise voluntary work, to strengthen the solidarity between young and old through best practices. It organizes of volunteer activities in order to provide social and independent life skills for children: homework duties, time planning, cleaning, cooking, self-reliance and choosing of possible future profession.

The foundations

We found very good work around the “universe” of communication. But we wanted to restrict the investigation area to the family unit. The closer we found at the time was a piece of work done by Université de Montréal doctoral student Marie-Josée Harbec and her supervisor, Professor Linda Pagani. “There is a handful of research suggesting positive links between eating family meals together frequently and child and adolescent health,” Pagani said. “In the past, researchers were unclear on whether families that ate together were simply healthier to begin with. And measuring how often families eat together and how children are doing at that very moment may not capture the complexity of the environmental experience.” Their findings were published after following a cohort of Quebec children born between 1997 and 1998 by the *Journal of Developmental & Behavioral Pediatrics* (2018). “Children who routinely eat their meals together with their family are more likely to experience long-term physical and mental health benefits”.

The study looked at children who had been followed by researchers since they were 5 months old as part of the Quebec Longitudinal Study of Child Development. At age 6, their parents started reporting on whether or not they had family meals together. At age 10, parents, teachers and the

children themselves provided information on the children's lifestyle habits and their psycho-social well-being.

"We decided to look at the long-term influence of sharing meals as an early childhood family environment experience in a sample of children born the same year," Pagani said, "and we followed-up regularly as they grew up. Using a birth cohort, this study examines the prospective associations between the environmental quality of the family meal experience at age 6 and child well-being at age 10."

When the family meal environment quality was better at age 6, higher levels of general fitness and lower levels of soft-drink consumption were observed at age 10. These children also seemed to have more social skills, as they were less likely to self-report being physical aggressive, oppositional or delinquent at age 10.

"Because we had a lot of information about the children before age 6 – such as their temperament and cognitive abilities, their mother's education and psychological characteristics, and prior family configuration and functioning – we were able to eliminate any pre-existing conditions of the children or families that could throw a different light on our results," said Harbec. "It was really ideal as a situation." Added professor Pagani: "The presence of parents during mealtimes likely provides young children with firsthand social interaction, discussions of social issues and day-to-day concerns, and vicarious learning of prosocial interactions in a familiar and emotionally secure setting. Experiencing positive forms of communication may likely help the child engage in better communication skills with people outside of the family unit. Our findings suggest that family meals are not solely markers of home environment quality, but are also easy targets for parent education about improving children's well-being."

The underline is ours, as this investigation was DIR most relevant foundation. The partnership assume there was a clear link between having dinner together and children's health and propose as hypothesis that cooking together could be the best daily time for enhancing family communication.

The management was granted to all partners, represented by the leading organization Fundacion Belen for all formal communications with the National Agency.

The Project coordinator is responsible to provide effective coordination and management of consortium to achieve project aims and objectives. Fundacion Belen has been working in close cooperation with managers of each partner in order to ensure effective and efficient financial management of the project and it will quarterly collect financial reports from partners on their real expenses.

Fundacion Belen will develop the progress and final reports to send to the National Agency, with the contribution of all partners in relationship to their own activities.

The concrete activities of DIR management and implementation can be resume as: prepare communication documents; organize the 8 Transnational Meetings; study the personal communication level of our low skilled mothers as well as their preferential form of learning through a questionnaire; compiling questionnaires and analyze results; select best method of learning communicational skills analysis per country; select senior volunteers to become coaches;

organize for them a training course by staff; create a work space for developing concepts and documents and finally prove to increase the personal communication level of mothers with uncommunicative children by cooking and dinner together workshops. We have already collect same first results in DVDs and analyze them in the International Meetings.

We need to disseminate the results, as we are trying by this paper as well as by DVDs, booklets and each institution website.

Based on Goleman's theory (1995) emotional intelligence includes knowing and managing personal emotions, sympathizing with others and handling communications in order to be satisfied with them. DIR have been working with senior volunteers trained as couches to teach management of personal emotions and communicational skills to stressed mothers by a cooking together experience that will work as learning mediator.

DIR partnership wanted to count on senior volunteers as they have extensive life experience to offer mothers and teenagers a close-knit, dialogic and empathetic position to change concerning habits such as their dietary habits, interacting at the table with family and peers, or whether or not one participates in setting or clearing the table and kitchen.

The willingness of senior volunteers can open the way for mothers and teenagers to realize more openly and empathetically through the cooking together experience that the meal time is important for providing support to the family relationships woven around the table. It is European life culture that enriches social personal life that should be preserved.

DIR has use the "cooking together experience" as a working tool of the learning by doing pathway.

Almost all studies emphasize on relationship between social skills and family relationships. For instance: In a study done by Jones, and Houts (1992) the results indicated that the effect of parental alcoholism on social skills of the adolescents must be considered in conjunction with specific types of family communication. Also, Burke, Woszildo, and Segrin (2013) concluded that the social skills and psychological problems of parents effect anxiety, loneliness and social skills of their children.

Questionnaires will be essential to determine whether we are on the right track of offering personal communication learning. After every cooking together experience workshop, we will deliver to trainees a satisfactory questionnaire and will aim to establish a communication test following the Family Communication Patterns Theory.

The DIR success will be assessed in the dissemination track by the information and DVDs will be produced during the cooking workshop. These outputs will show if DIR is obtaining positive results within families with communication problems

Certificates of Recognition will also be a measure of success, and the interest and take-up of the learning pathways by all levels of strategic partners.

DIR project has three target primary groups for the DIR results dissemination activities at all levels: Between senior volunteers, showing that with a special preparation they can become personal coaches with new chances of social service and active life. The dissemination at local

level will be guaranteed by the Local Group Collaborator; at National Level will be to produce through National Volunteers Associations; at European Level by each partner web site.

Between distressed mothers, demonstrating that enhancing personal communication skill is a good way for personal and social empowerment as well as a good way to improve and be recognized for their cooking skills. DIR dissemination results at local level will be guaranteed by the Local Group Collaborator; at National Level will be produced through National Parents Associations; at European Level by each partner web site.

And between uncommunicative teenagers, we will pioneer new methods of improving personal communicational skill as a new way to enhance the family and peer relationship. The dissemination at local level will be guaranteed by the Local Group Collaborator; and at National Level through Youth Institutes; at European Level by each partner web site.

To educational staff, DIR project results will show new ways of teaching and training. The dissemination at local level will be guaranteed by the Local Group Collaborator; at National Level will be produced through media and newspaper; at European Level by each partner web site.

The dissemination activities will start after the beginning of the project. Project partners will place information about the project on their organization websites. Dissemination will be intensified after the Kick off meeting.

The Local Collaborator Groups (LCGs) will be selected in each of the four European cities by the local DIR partner. The LCGs members will come from diverse backgrounds (teachers, social workers, doctors, nurses, older people). Each one of these groups has different capacities and has their own atmosphere. Together will enrich the final outputs and will contribute to reach all areas of society, especially the most vulnerable groups, becoming a part of the local culture, shaping the local environment as the DIR cooking experience culture irrigate the society.

As the target groups for DIR are senior volunteers, stressed mothers and uncommunicated youngsters the partners will reach them where normally they meet: associations, libraries, local canteens, religious organizations. This initial effort should improve the final dissemination process.

The uncommunication level between parents and siblings and between teachers and pupils is a major social European problem.

Almost all studies emphasize on relationship between social skills and family relationships. For instance: In a study done by Jones, and Houts (1992) the results indicated that the effect of parental alcoholism on social skills of the adolescents must be considered in conjunction with specific types of family communication. Also, Burke, Woszildo, and Segrin (2013) reached the conclusion that social skills and psychological problems of parents influence anxiety, loneliness and social skills of their children. In a study done by Arroyo, Nevarez, Segrin, and Harwood (2012) results show that parent and teenagers lacking communication were negatively associated with their own social skills. In addition, teenager's social skills were significantly associated with perceived family communication.

Family communication can be measured by a scale and can be used for various families. The questions of this scale included: communication style, expressing feelings, cooperation, sharing

problems with each other, viewing with each other, sincerely answering, perception of feelings’ each other, anger control and genuine expression of emotions.

DIR questionnaire

After some discussions during the Madrid Kick Off Meeting the partners agree on the 20 questions proposed by Fundación Belen questionnaire, as well as the proposition of offering only two possible answers “yes” or “not”. Partners decided not to offer a scale 1 to 5 in order to press the parents for defining themselves clearly.

1. Do you speak daily to your adolescent child?
2. Do you listen to him/her every day at least 10 minutes?
3. Do you know the names of his/her teachers?
4. Do you know which are his/her favorite subjects?
5. Do you know the names of his/her friends and “enemies”?
6. What kind of music does he/she listen to?
7. What food does he/she like?
8. Do you have dinner together every day?
9. Do you often share games or sports with your son/daughter?
10. Do you go with him/her to the doctor?
11. Do you know what ailments he/she has and what medicines does he/she take?
12. Do you know how to share your feelings and talk about your problems with your adolescent child?
13. Can you speak with him/her about sensitive matters (sex, drugs, gangs, etc...)?
14. Do you share with your adolescent dreams, desires and yearnings?
15. Does your son/daughter tell you what worries him/her?
16. Can you perceive what hurts or angers him/her?
17. Do you know how to punish him/her fairly and constructively?
18. Are you capable of dominating your anger without hurting him/her?
19. Do you know how to reward his/her good behavior?
20. Do you travel and have fun together on holidays?

From a extend point of view there are not big differences looking through the three columns of answers. It looks like three parallel roads travelling through our European teenagers. The positive answers in percentage looks like a picture of “European young parents characteristics”.

But if we look near and carefully there are country’s differences.

For instance	FB	ARVAR	NALMA
18. Are you capable of dominating your anger?	47	74	71
15. Does your son tell you what worries him/her?	56	81	73
8. Do you often share games or sports with him?	40	72	26
7. Do you have dinner together every day?	65	44	38

Our group of senior volunteers favour DIR a intergenerationalism approach

According to Margaret Mead "Connections between generations are essential for the mental health and stability of a nation". The young and the old share a different rhythm. It is one that focuses not only on doing, but on the power of being. The young and the old are most closely connected with the essence of living. Rather than time being the enemy, senior volunteers find time a comfortable companion, a new space for freedom.

Generally, our society divides our communities and our activities by age: young people in schools, older people in retirement communities or alone at home. If we can encourage the standing of older adults as senior volunteers, and nurture what they can bring through intergenerational connections, then we can achieve a better community with a better quality of life for all ages.

Historically, young and old connected naturally. Older people taught the young how to be and how to become a person. Close daily contact between the young and old was a matter of survival. Being with, watching after, and assisting in the care of young children, while demanding in many ways, does not require but love and experience. The physical limitations that can come while ageing may cement the relationship between senior and teenagers, with daily of examples of nearness between grandparents and grandchildren. There is a back-and-forth reciprocity between all generations.

Seniors volunteers can be greatest teachers. They can certainly instruct youngsters with cooking recipes, stories of times past to communicate dinning together and share manners and wisdom. The benefits to siblings of a close, long-term connection with grandparents include having a better sense of who they are and where they have come from; it gives roots, history, and a sense of continuity and perspective. In general, children develop higher self-esteem, better emotional and social skills (including communication) and can even have better grades in school.

A relationship with a grandchild or young friend gives older adults a "second chance." Active, involved older adults with close intergenerational connections consistently report much less depression, better physical health, and higher degrees of life satisfaction. They tend to be happier with their present life and more hopeful for the future.

Relationships across generations

The richest forms of human development are most available to those willing and able to interweave their needs and potential with the needs and potential of others, especially those younger or older.

The success of isolated intergenerational projects and programs across Europe clearly demonstrates the significant benefits of intergenerational contact to both children and adults.

The challenge now lies in going beyond a project or program here or there to making a larger commitment to intergenerational connections so that they become a part of daily life and the social fabric. There are many good examples of intergenerational learning, some short and spasmodic, but the inspirational ones are of longer duration, require more intense commitment and initial investment so as not to lead to disappointment and not achieving objectives. Where a "living together" arrangement based on old-style community relationships of years gone-by have been attempted they require intense investment but already show a model for generations living together

influencing and providing role models to younger generations whilst at the same time using the basic skills of communication, numeracy, literacy and information technology to add value to family life.

We hope and trust that our DIR project will add to the debate on Social Return on Investment by showing the positive measurable outcomes which we have achieved.

Our transnational meetings in Madrid (Spain) Bucharest (Romania) Kaunas (Lithuania) and Lichfield (United Kingdom) have been most educational in showing us where inspiration and innovation are being applied to these specific needs so our project is constantly evolving and our outcomes are fluid enough to be able to incorporate the best practice we are finding in each country, review, assess and incorporate them into our final report.

Our results so far (we have another 12 months to continue our project) lead us to believe that a communication learning pathway is needed carried out by mentors and senior volunteers. We anticipate the results of our project to be a better understanding of the development needs of parents of disenfranchised adolescents.

References

Harbec, Marie-Josée & Pagani, Linda (2017). Associations between early family meal environment quality and later well-being in school age children. December 2017 issue of the *Journal of Developmental & Behavioral Pediatrics*.